

Enhance driver behaviour & Public Acceptance
of Connected & Autonomous vehicles

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D3.3 – CAVA – Connected and Autonomous Vehicles Acceptance Assessment Tool

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List of acronyms	
Acronym	Meaning
CAV	Connected and Autonomous Vehicles
CAVA	Connected and Autonomous Vehicle Acceptance Assessment Tool
EBU	European Blind Union
CFA	Confirmatory Factor Analysis
EFA	Exploratory Factor Analysis
KMO	Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure
CCAM	Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility

Notice

This document complies with the European Blind Union’s guidelines (<http://www.euroblind.org/publications-and-resources/making-information-accessible-all>) in order to be accessible to anyone, including blind and partially sighted people, and at the same time and at no additional cost.

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Executive summary

The PAsCAL project, funded under the "Horizon 2020" Research and Innovation program, has the goal to provide insights and develop a better understanding about citizens' and stakeholders' expectations for connected and automated vehicles (CAVs), and the acceptance of CAVs. The following deliverable introduces the Connected and Autonomous Vehicle Acceptance Assessment Tool (CAVA) developed in WP3. The aim of the CAVA is to measure autonomous vehicle acceptance via evaluation of expected autonomous vehicle consequences. With the aim to allow a modular use of the tool, it was construed to assess distinct factors of acceptance in diverse populations. It was developed in a multi-method approach, and the tool was validated in a large-scale survey with over 5000 participants from 11 countries. The validation study yielded very good indices for validity, reliability and fit of the measurement instrument. In the deliverable, we report benchmarks for different factors and populations. For a most flexible use, we add an interactive tool allowing CAVA users to retrieve benchmarks based on specific subsamples and factors useful for a variety of data collections. Possible use cases are presented to illustrate the usage of the CAVA by researchers, policy makers and industry partners.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and organization of the document

The following document, D3.3, aims to provide an introduction to the Connected and Autonomous Vehicle Acceptance Assessment Tool (CAVA) developed in WP3 over the course of the PAScAL project. The aim of the CAVA is to measure CAV acceptance via evaluation of expected CAV consequences. It consists of different subscales allowing to assess distinct factors of CAV acceptance, which makes it applicable to different research foci and user populations.

D3.3 also aims to provide insights into how the survey was employed for data collection, provide indices for validity, reliability and fit (i.e., whether the proposed models **fit** the data) of the measurement instrument, and some possible use cases for further usage of the CAVA.

Finally, the deliverable provides benchmark values for future researchers that wish to employ the survey items to collect their own data and compare their specific subsamples to either representatively drawn populations that match their needs, or track changes in acceptance of CAVs.

Following the Introduction (Chapter 1), the document is divided into six main sections:

In Chapter 2, we shall describe the process of survey generation and evolution towards the final version of the CAVA. Additionally, the survey as it was used to collect the benchmark dataset is presented and described in detail. A table with all survey items is supplied.

In Chapter 3, we introduce some case examples for how parties of interest can potentially employ the CAVA for their purposes, be it policy or research.

In Chapter 4, a thorough evaluation of validity, reliability and fit indices of the items in the context of the conducted confirmatory factor analysis is presented to showcase the measurement quality of the Connected and Autonomous Vehicle Acceptance Assessment Tool.

Chapter 5 presents a wide variety of benchmark values that can be used by future researchers to compare their own findings against.

Finally, Chapter 6 provides a brief summary, discussion and section on limitations.

1.2 Intended audience of this document

The audience for this document are (1) the consortium members of the PAsCAL project, specifically partners responsible for the different CAV trials, simulations, pilots, CAV training skills development and development of business cases, (2) policymakers, specifically those with an interest in creating a more participatory CAV introduction that suits the needs of a variety of subpopulations, and (3) researchers of both academic and industry settings and part of the Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility Association (CCAM) with an interest in CAV acceptance measures as well as motivators and barriers to CAV integration.

The wider research community is invited to use survey items, benchmarks and insights from the conceptual side to extend their research into appropriate CAV solutions based on the recommendations, in particular when approaching varying target groups and multiple geographical locations.

A main objective of the PAsCAL project is to move the focus towards a more user-centric design of CAV research, so development of a tool that enables collection of data on citizens' attitudes across a wide range of demographics, locations and expected consequences should facilitate this objective.

2 Acceptance Assessment Tool Description

2.1 CAVA – Description of survey instrument

2.1.1 Survey construction

The Connected and Autonomous Vehicle acceptance survey was developed in multiple steps. Firstly, as reported in D3.1, a large item pool was generated based on a wide variety of consequences expected from the introduction of CAVs as described in the scientific literature (Anderson et al., 2016; Golbabaie et al., 2020; Hancock, 2019; Kacperski et al., 2020; Nordhoff et al., 2019). The full item pool can be accessed in D3.1. These items were presented to a panel participant pool of about 600 participants in a first validation round.

Items from this survey were used to develop a Model of Expected Consequences of CAV Introduction; an exploratory factor analysis on data collected across four EU countries (Germany, France, Italy, UK) yielded that out of an original 53 items, 15 should be retained, spanning the four factors Safety, Sustainability, Efficiency and Privacy. The analyses that were carried out on this first dataset showed that the data was very well suited in terms of sampling adequacy, held sufficient correlation in the data. Acceptable discriminant validity and excellent reliabilities, as well as very good fit indices of a follow-up confirmatory factor analysis supported that those 15 items should be retained. All analyses can be found in a peer-reviewed scientific publication (see Kacperski et al., 2021).

In addition to consequence-related items, items related to general and affective evaluations, behavioural intentions to use and ease of use of CAVs were supplied; a structural equation model showcased very good predictive power from the consequence items to participants' attitudes and intentions to use CAVs for all factors (Kacperski et al., 2021).

A second data set of 115 visually impaired participants, collected with the help of the European Blind Union's German representatives, was used to compare their attitudes to those of sighted German participants recruited via a panel. Results led to the conclusion that an additional factor was necessary, the factor Independence, represented via five additional items from the original 53 items, including social and economic participation, and a comfort component. Similarly to the findings above, a confirmatory factor analysis supported this choice with very good reliability and fit indices (Kacperski et al., under review).

Following these analyses, and further deliberation with consortium partners, particularly representatives from the European Blind Union, two further items specifically assessing Accessibility, two items developed to measure Road Co-user (particularly pedestrian) Safety, and two items representing the Cost of the CAV journeys, were included for a novel round of validations. The final item list can be found in Chapter 2.2.

These items, including once again items targeting general, cognitive and affective evaluation and behavioural intention to use, as well as ease of use, were presented in a shorter survey to over 4800 participants from 8 European countries via a panel service, and to over 800 more visually impaired participants recruited via representatives of the European Blind Union.

Deliverable 3.2 supplies a first insight into findings from this survey data collection, providing descriptive and summary statistics to better delve into how different participants felt about the consequences of connected and autonomous vehicles.

The final tool, in the form of a short survey for easy administration and economical usage, is showcased in 2.1.2 in detail, with all items presented in Chapter 2.2. Chapter 3 will then summarize a few different use cases to showcase how the Connected and Autonomous Vehicle Acceptance Assessment can be employed in a modular fashion to collect meaningful results from a variety of contexts, ranging from interests by policymakers, industry partners, academics to mobility experts and lay users.

2.1.2 Survey description (text and screenshots)

In the following section, we shall describe the survey: Participants were invited via a panel service, which we employed to gather a stratified sample (by age/ gender crossed, and education if possible). On the start page, each participant could select the language that was most comfortable for them (see [Figure 1](#)). The questionnaire was conducted online and took between 10-20 minutes to complete (see also [Figure 2](#)).

Figure 1 Language selection.

Figure 2 Introduction

Before starting the survey, participants gave informed consent for voluntary participation, data use, and data storage in accordance with

ethics requirements by the German psychology association (DGPS) and DGPR guidelines (see [Figure 3](#)).

The screenshot shows a survey page with the following elements:

- Horizon 2020 European Union Funding for Research & Innovation logo and text.
- A progress bar indicating 6% completion.
- A button labeled "Change to more accessible version".
- A section header: **Data protection and consent to participate**.
- Text: "Before you participate, we would like to ask you to give your consent to the following points."
- Text: "I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I can end my participation at any time without having to give a reason for it and without this restricting my rights."
- Text: "I understand that my data from this questionnaire will be saved by the researchers, at least until the requirements for publishing one or more articles in a journal are met. This includes my consent to this."
- Text: "I agree that my anonymous data will be used and shared for research purposes (e.g. in publications, journals etc.)."
- Text: "I agree to participate in the study that is before me."
- A checkbox with the text: "I consent to the above points." (The checkbox is currently unchecked).
- Text at the bottom: "If you do not agree, you may leave the survey now."

Figure 3 Data protection and consent to participate.

After that, participants were randomly assigned to one of two conditions, varying the target solution: personal autonomous cars vs. shared autonomous cars. For the sake of clarity, all of the following sections and figures refer to the "personal autonomous car" solution (see [Figure 4](#)).

The screenshot shows a web page header with the Horizon 2020 logo and text: "Horizon 2020 European Union Funding for Research & Innovation". To the right is a progress bar labeled "12% completed". Below the header is a button that says "Change to more accessible version". The main heading is "Autonomous and connected cars". The text below explains that autonomous cars are not controlled by a human driver and automatically control all actions. It then asks participants to imagine owning their own personal autonomous car, listing four conditions: purchasing it yourself, parking it on their premises, being responsible for it, and having it available 100% of the time.

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Autonomous and connected cars

Ever more autonomous cars are introduced on our roads. These cars **are not controlled by a human driver**. Instead, they are completely controlled by a computer system. An autonomous car takes over all tasks and **automatically controls all actions, including steering, acceleration and braking**.

In the following we will ask you to imagine **owning** your own personal autonomous car.

As it is **your personal autonomous car**,

- you will **purchase it yourself**,
- it is **parked** on your premises,
- you are **responsible** for it,
- and it is **available** to you 100% of the time.

Figure 4 Information presented to participants in the “personal autonomous car” solution.

In terms of content, participants first indicated their intention to use personal autonomous cars on 4 items. Responses were collected on a 7-point scale (“disagree completely” to “agree completely”; see [Figure 5](#)).

[Change to more accessible version](#)

Intentions to use personal autonomous cars

Please indicate your agreement to the following statements:

	disagree completely	agree completely
I would not like to use my autonomous car.	○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○	
I would try to avoid personal autonomous cars as much as possible.	○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○	
If personal autonomous cars were available, I would use them.	○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○	
I would be willing to use my autonomous car.	○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○	

Figure 5 Intention to use.

Second, participants indicated the ease of use on 2 items. Responses were collected on a 7-point scale ("disagree completely" to "agree completely"; see Figure 6).

The screenshot shows a survey interface. At the top left is the Horizon 2020 logo with the text 'Horizon 2020 European Union Funding for Research & Innovation'. To the right is a progress bar labeled '24% completed'. Below the logo is a button that says 'Change to more accessible version'. The main heading is 'Ease of use'. Below this is the instruction 'Please indicate your agreement to the following statements:'. There are two statements, each with a 7-point Likert scale. The first statement is 'I think I could handle my autonomous car well.' and the second is 'I can imagine that I would have problems using my autonomous car.' The scales are labeled 'disagree completely' on the left and 'agree completely' on the right. The second statement and its scale are highlighted with a grey background.

Figure 6 Ease of use.

Third, participants indicated their general evaluation of personal autonomous cars on 4 items (7-point scales; see [Figure 7](#)). They answered...

- ... whether they find the thought of their personal autonomous car generally disconcerting or promising.
- ... whether they find their personal autonomous car very bad or very good in general.
- ... whether they would prefer conventional vehicles or their personal autonomous car as a means of transportation.
- ... whether their spontaneous attitude towards their personal autonomous car was very negative or very positive.

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Your general evaluation

Please indicate your opinion on the following statements:

The thought of my autonomous car is generally... disconcerting ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ promising

In principle, I would find personal autonomous cars ... very bad ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ very good

As a means of transportation I would prefer... the conventional variant ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ my autonomous car

My spontaneous attitude towards my autonomous car is... very negative ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ very positive

Figure 7 General evaluation

Fourth, participants indicated their cognitive evaluation of personal autonomous cars on 4 items. Responses were collected on a 7-point scale ("does not apply at all" to "applies completely"; see [Figure 8](#)).

Change to more accessible version

Your thoughts about personal autonomous cars

Please imagine that large sections of the population would use their own autonomous cars.

To what degree do the following statements apply to you?

	does not apply at all	applies completely
I think large sections of the population using their own autonomous cars would be unnecessary.	○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○	
I think if large sections of the population would use their own autonomous cars this would be useful.	○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○	
I think if large sections of the population would use their own autonomous cars this would be beneficial.	○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○	
I think if large sections of the population would use their own autonomous cars this would be harmful.	○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○	

Figure 8 Cognitive evaluation

Fifth, participants indicated their affective evaluation of personal autonomous cars on 4 items. Responses were collected on a 7-point scale ("does not apply at all" to "applies completely"; see [Figure 9](#)).

41% completed

Change to more accessible version

Your feelings about personal autonomous cars

Please imagine that large sections of the population would use their own autonomous cars.

To what degree do the following statements apply to you?

	does not apply at all	applies completely
This item is an attention test. Please answer "applies completely".	○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○	
I feel it would be great if large sections of the population used their own autonomous cars.	○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○	
I feel it would be stressful if large sections of the population used their own autonomous cars.	○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○	
The idea that large sections of the population use their own autonomous cars feels bad.	○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○	
The idea that large sections of the population use their own autonomous cars feels good.	○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○ ○	

Figure 9 Affective evaluation and an attention check item

The participants were finally asked to imagine a time in which large sections of the population use autonomous vehicles, and to express their agreement with a list of 19 statements (7-point scales). The statements were designed to assess the consequences of personal autonomous cars (see Figures 10.1-10.5).

A full list of the items is available in Chapter 2.2 of the present document.

[Change to more accessible version](#)

Consequences

Note: Graphic shows a multitude of cars emitting a wireless signal, and a group of diverse people standing next to them.

If I used my autonomous car, my costs per journey would be... higher lower.

If large sections of the population used their own autonomous cars, the number of traffic accidents involving pedestrians, bicyclists or other road co-users would be... higher lower

If I used my autonomous car, I would be, at work,... less productive more productive

If large sections of the population used their own autonomous cars, travel for all citizens would be... more dangerous less dangerous

Figure 10 Consequences

Change to more accessible version

Consequences

Note: Graphic shows a multitude of cars emitting a wireless signal, and a group of diverse people standing next to them.

If large sections of the population used their own autonomous cars, the travel time of citizens would be... longer shorter

If large sections of the population used their own autonomous cars, pedestrians would be... more at risk less at risk

If large sections of the population used their own autonomous cars, the number of traffic accidents would be... higher lower

If I used my autonomous car, I would be... slower faster

Figure 10.2. Consequences – Page 2.

[Change to more accessible version](#)

Consequences

Note: Graphic shows a multitude of cars emitting a wireless signal, and a group of diverse people standing next to them.

If I used my autonomous car, my attendance at events (e.g. concerts, parties) would be...

less frequent more frequent

If I used my autonomous car my life satisfaction would be...

lower higher.

If I used my autonomous car, my personal data would be...

less secure more secure

If large sections of the population used their own autonomous cars, greenhouse gas emissions would be...

higher lower

Figure 10.3. Consequences – Page 3.

[Change to more accessible version](#)

Consequences

Note: Graphic shows a multitude of cars emitting a wireless signal, and a group of diverse people standing next to them.

If large sections of the population used their own autonomous cars, the pollution caused by exhaust gases and particles would be... higher lower

If large sections of the population used their own autonomous cars, for people with disabilities, mobility would be... less accessible more accessible

If I used my autonomous car, my travelling experience would be... less pleasant more pleasant.

If I used my autonomous car, my total mobility costs would be... higher lower

Figure 10.4. Consequences – Page 4.

[Change to more accessible version](#)

Consequences

Note: Graphic shows a multitude of cars emitting a wireless signal, and a group of diverse people standing next to them.

If I used my autonomous car for travel, I would need...

less assistance more assistance

If I used my autonomous car, the risk that my personal data were misused would be ...

higher lower

If I used my autonomous car, meetings with friends, family would be ...

less frequent more frequent

Figure 10.5. Consequences – Page 5.

Upon completion, participants provided information regarding their experience with autonomous cars (see [Figure 11](#)).

The screenshot shows a survey interface. At the top left is the Horizon 2020 logo with the text 'Horizon 2020 European Union Funding for Research & Innovation'. To the right is a progress bar labeled '96% completed'. Below the logo is a button that says 'Change to more accessible version'. The main title of the survey is 'Your experience with autonomous cars'. Below the title, it asks 'Please indicate the following:'. The question is 'I have used autonomous technologies before, namely...'. There are six radio button options listed below the question.

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96% completed

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Your experience with autonomous cars

Please indicate the following:

I have used autonomous technologies before, namely...

- a function in my/a car.
- a completely autonomous car.
- a completely autonomous shuttle or a minibus.
- a completely autonomous bus.
- a completely autonomous train or metro.
- I have never used autonomous technology.

Figure 11 Experience with autonomous cars

Participants were then asked about the use/ avoidance of personal or shared autonomous cars on 4 items. Responses were collected on a 7-point scale ("disagree completely" to "agree completely"; see [Figure 12](#)).

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71% completed

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Owned or Shared?

Please indicate the following:

	disagree completely	agree completely
If autonomous cars were available as shared mobility (such as car-sharing), I would try to avoid them as much as possible.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
If autonomous cars were available as owned, personal vehicles, I would try to avoid them as much as possible.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
If autonomous cars were available as owned, personal vehicles, I would use them.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
If autonomous cars were available as shared mobility (such as car-sharing), I would use them.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Figure 12 Use/ avoidance of personal or shared autonomous cars

Next, participants provided information regarding their mobility status: number of cars in their household, whether they have a driving licence, whether they use public transport/ car sharing/ ride providers regularly (see [Figure 13](#)).

[Change to more accessible version](#)

Your Mobility

Number of cars in your household:

- No car
- 1 car
- 2 cars
- More than 2 cars

Do you have a driver's license?

- Yes, I have a currently valid driver's license.
- No, I do not have a currently valid driver's license.

Do you use public transport (i.e. bus, train, tram, subway) regularly?

- Yes, I use public transport at least once a month or more.
- No, I use public transport less than once a month.

Do you use car sharing regularly?

- Yes, I use car sharing at least once a month or more.
- No, I use car sharing less than once a month.

Do you use ride providers (such as taxicabs, Uber) regularly?

- Yes, I use ride providers at least once a month or more.
- No, I use ride providers less than once a month.

Figure 13 Mobility.

A series of following questions assessed whether participants had a visual impairment and how often they left their house for longer than 10 minutes (Figure 14.1). If the answer to the first question was “Yes”, more in-depth questions were asked on the next page (Figure 14.2).

The screenshot shows a survey form with the following elements:

- Logo for Horizon 2020 European Union Funding for Research & Innovation.
- A progress bar indicating 79% completion.
- A button labeled "Change to more accessible version".
- A section header "Visual impairment".
- An introductory text: "In the following we would like to ask you about your eyesight."
- A question: "Do you have a visual impairment?" with four radio button options:
 - No.
 - Yes, I am blind.
 - Yes, I am partially-sighted.
 - Yes, I am deaf-blind.
- A second question: "How often do you leave your home for longer than 10 minutes?" with six radio button options:
 - Several times a day
 - Once a day
 - 4 to 6 days a week
 - 2 to 3 days a week
 - Once a week
 - More seldom than once a week

Figure 14. Visual impairment.

[Change to more accessible version](#)

Visual impairment - Other questions

When did your visual impairment start?

- I was born visually impaired.
- The visual impairment occurred later in life.

I travel familiar paths...

- alone.
- with difficulties.
- only in the company of another person.

I travel unfamiliar paths...

- alone.
- with difficulties.
- only in the company of another person.

Do you use one or more of the following tools (multiple answers possible)?

- I do not use any tools.
- White cane
- GPS
- Guide dog
- sighted accompaniment/assistance
- Other (please specify)

Figure 15 Visual impairment.

Demographic characteristics such as gender, age, location, etc. were also collected (see [Figure 16](#)).

89% completed

[Change to more accessible version](#)

Information about yourself

Finally, we would like to ask you for some information about yourself.

Gender:

You are...

female

male

diverse, namely

Age:

You are... years old.

Which country do you currently live in?

You live in:

What are the first THREE digits/letters of your post code?

Your post code starts with the digits ** (only the first 3 digits please)

What is your current employment status?

Student / Vocational training

Employee / Civil servant

Self-employed

Unemployed / Looking for work

Other:

Figure 16 Demographic variables.

Is driving part of your job?

No.

Yes.

What educational level do you have?

Please choose the highest educational qualification you have achieved so far.

No school leaving certificate

Elementary or lower secondary school qualification

Middle School, High School or Secondary School, Completed apprenticeship

Advanced Vocational Certificate of Education, Technical diploma, A levels, High School diploma or Other university entrance qualification

Polytechnic degree, University of applied sciences degree, Other university degree

What is your household's monthly net income approximately?

What is meant is the amount that is made up of all income and remains after the deduction of taxes and social insurance.

less than € 250

€ 250 to under € 1000

€ 1000 to under € 2000

€ 2000 to under € 3000

€ 3000 to under € 5000

€ 5000 and over

I do not want to answer that

Household size:

Number of people in your household:

Figure 17 Demographic variables continuation

Before being directed to the last page (see [Figure 19](#)), participants were asked how COVID-19 affected them and their thoughts about autonomous vehicles (see [Figure 18](#)).

[Change to more accessible version](#)

Corona virus and autonomous vehicles

In the following, we would like to know more about how COVID-19 has affected you and your thoughts about autonomous vehicles.

The COVID-19 crisis...	does not at all apply	applies fully
is negatively affecting my life overall.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
negatively influences my economic situation.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
has a negative impact on my mobility.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
in my opinion will soon be over.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
If I were to use my autonomous car during the COVID-19 crisis, my general situation would be...	worse <input type="radio"/>	better. <input type="radio"/>
If I were to use my autonomous car during the COVID-19 crisis, my economic situation would be...	worse <input type="radio"/>	better. <input type="radio"/>
If I were to use my autonomous car during the COVID-19 crisis, I would be...	less mobile <input type="radio"/>	more mobile. <input type="radio"/>

Please let us know if you have already been infected with COVID-19.

No, I do not think so.

I am not sure.

I have the feeling I was already infected.

I was tested positive for COVID-19.

I do not want to answer.

Figure 18 Corona virus and autonomous cars.

Figure 19 End of survey.

2.1.3 Survey description (text only for visually impaired participants)

In the following section, we will briefly describe the survey: Participants were invited via a panel service, which we employed to gather a stratified sample (by age/ gender crossed, and education if possible). On the start page, each participant could select the language that was most comfortable for him/ her (see [Figure 1](#)). The questionnaire was conducted online and took between 10-20 minutes to complete (see also [Figure 2](#)).

Before starting the survey, participants gave informed consent for voluntary participation, data use, and data storage in accordance with ethics requirements by the German psychology association (DGPS) and DGPR guidelines (see [Figure 3](#)). After that, participants were randomly assigned to one of two conditions, varying the target solution: personal autonomous cars vs. shared autonomous cars. For the sake of clarity, all of the following sections and figures refer to the "personal autonomous car" solution (see [Figure 4](#)).

In terms of content, participants first indicated their intention to use personal autonomous cars on 4 items. Responses were collected on a 7-point scale ("*disagree completely*" to "*agree completely*"; see [Figure 5](#)). Second, participants indicated the ease of use on 2 items. Responses were collected on a 7-point scale ("*disagree completely*" to "*agree completely*"; see [Figure 6](#)). Third, participants indicated their general

evaluation of personal autonomous cars on 4 items (7-point scales; see [Figure 7](#)). They answered...

- ... whether they find the thought of their personal autonomous car generally disconcerting or promising.
- ... whether they find their personal autonomous car very bad or very good in general.
- ... whether they would prefer conventional vehicles or their personal autonomous car as a means of transportation.
- ... whether their spontaneous attitude towards their personal autonomous car was very negative or very positive.

Fourth, participants indicated their cognitive evaluation of personal autonomous cars on 4 items. Responses were collected on a 7-point scale (*"does not apply at all"* to *"applies completely"*; see [Figure 8](#)). Fifth, participants indicated their affective evaluation of personal autonomous cars on 4 items. Responses were collected on a 7-point scale (*"does not apply at all"* to *"applies completely"*; see [Figure 9](#)). The participants were finally asked to imagine a time in which large sections of the population use autonomous vehicles, and to express their agreement with a list of 19 statements (7-point scales). The statements were designed to assess the consequences of personal autonomous cars (see [Figures 10.1-10.5](#)). A list of most relevant items is available in Section 2.2 of the present document.

Upon completion, participants provided information regarding their experience with autonomous cars (see [Figure 11](#)). Participants were then asked about the use/ avoidance of personal or shared autonomous cars on 4 items. Responses were collected on a 7-point scale (*"disagree completely"* to *"agree completely"*; see [Figure 12](#)). Next, participants provided information regarding their mobility status: number of cars in their household, whether they have a driving licence, whether they use public transport/ car sharing/ ride providers regularly (see [Figure 13](#)). A series of following questions assessed whether participants had a visual impairment and how often they left their house for longer than 10 minutes ([Figure 14.1](#)). If the answer to the first question was "Yes", more in-depth questions were asked on the next page ([Figure 15](#)). Demographic characteristics such as gender, age, location, etc. were also collected (see [Figure 16 and 17](#)). Before being directed to the last page (see [Figure 19](#)), participants were asked how COVID-19 affected them and their thoughts about autonomous vehicles (see [Figure 18](#)).

2.2 Survey items tables

2.2.1 Intention to use CAVs

Please indicate your agreement to the following statements: [disagree completely 1 – 7 agree completely]
If autonomous vehicles were available, I would use them.
I would try to avoid autonomous vehicles as much as possible.
I would not like to use autonomous vehicles.
I would be willing to use autonomous vehicles.

2.2.2 Ease of Use

Please indicate your agreement to the following statements: [disagree completely 1 – 7 agree completely]
I think I could handle autonomous vehicles well.
I can imagine that I would have problems using autonomous vehicles.

2.2.3 General evaluation of autonomous vehicles

The thought of autonomous vehicles is generally... [1 – 7]
disconcerting
promising
In principle, I would find autonomous vehicles ...
very bad
very good
My spontaneous attitude towards autonomous vehicles is...
very negative

very positive
As a means of transportation, I would prefer...
the conventional variant
autonomous vehicles

2.2.4 Cognitive evaluation

To what degree do the following statements apply to you? [does not apply at all 1 – 7 does not apply at all]
I think if large sections of the population would use autonomous vehicles this would be beneficial.
I think if large sections of the population would use autonomous vehicles this would be harmful.
I think if large sections of the population would use autonomous vehicles this would be useful.
I think large sections of the population using autonomous vehicles would be unnecessary.

2.2.5 Affective evaluation

To what degree do the following statements apply to you? [does not apply at all 1 – 7 does not apply at all]
The idea that large sections of the population use autonomous vehicles feels bad.
The idea that large sections of the population use autonomous vehicles feels good.
I feel it would be stressful if large sections of the population used autonomous vehicles.

I feel it would be great if large sections of the population used autonomous vehicles.

2.2.6 Consequences of autonomous vehicles

Please imagine a time in which large sections of the population use autonomous vehicles. What effect do you think this would have? [1 – 7]

DATA_PRIVACY: If I used autonomous vehicles, my personal data would be... less secure/more secure

DATA_PRIVACY: If I used autonomous vehicles, the risk that my personal data were misused would be ... higher/lower

ROAD_SAFETY: If large sections of the population used autonomous vehicles, travel for all citizens would be... more dangerous/less dangerous.

ROAD_SAFETY: If large sections of the population used autonomous vehicles, the number of traffic accidents would be... higher/lower.

TRAVEL_TIME: If I used autonomous vehicles I would be... slower/faster.

TRAVEL_TIME: If large sections of the population used autonomous vehicles, the travel time of the citizens would be... longer/shorter.

EMISSIONS: If large sections of the population used autonomous vehicles, greenhouse gas emissions would be... higher/lower.

EMISSIONS: If large sections of the population used autonomous vehicles, the pollution caused by exhaust gases and particles would be... higher/lower.

SOCIAL_LIFE: If I used autonomous vehicles, my attendance at events (e.g. concerts, parties) would be... less frequent/more frequent.

SOCIAL_LIFE: If I used autonomous vehicles, meetings with friends, family... would be less frequent/more frequent.

AFFECT: If I used autonomous vehicles, my travelling experience would be... less pleasant/more pleasant.

LIFE_QUALITY: If I used autonomous vehicles my life satisfaction would be... lower/higher.

JOB_PERFORMANCE: If I used autonomous vehicles, I would be, at work,... less productive/more productive.

TRAVEL_COSTS: If I used autonomous vehicles, my costs per journey would be... higher/lower.

TRAVEL_COSTS: If I used autonomous vehicles, my total mobility costs would be... higher/lower.

COUSER_SAFETY: If large sections of the population used autonomous vehicles, pedestrians would be... more at risk/less at risk.

COUSER_SAFETY: If large sections of the population used autonomous vehicles, the number of traffic accidents involving pedestrians, bicyclists or other road co-users would be... Higher/lower.

ACCESSIBILITY: If large sections of the population used autonomous vehicles, for people with disabilities, mobility would be less accessible/more accessible.

ACCESSIBILITY: If I used autonomous vehicles for travel, I would need less assistance/more assistance.

2.3 Survey – sample description

In total we collected 5661 participants, of which 4858 were participants recruited by a panel provider that has access to representatively drawn samples across many countries, and 801 participants were recruited by the European Blind Union’s member states among their constituents.

The following tables showcases the gender distributions across the different countries, in Table 1 for participants from the panel and in Table 2 for participants for EBU-recruited participants.

Table 1. Gender distribution for panel sample.

	Gender	diverse	men	women	Totals
Country					
Austria			99	100	199
Belgium		2	120	103	225
France		2	404	404	810
Germany			518	514	1,032
Hungary			101	98	199
Italy			387	375	762
Portugal			100	101	201
Spain		1	289	290	580
UK		6	418	426	850
Totals		11	2,436	2,411	4,858

Table 2. Gender distribution for EBU-recruited individuals.

	Gender	diverse	men	women	Totals
Country					
Czech Republic			50	24	74
Germany			32	27	59
Hungary			71	65	136
Italy		1	46	31	78
Lithuania			30	47	77
Macedonia			33	8	41
Portugal			95	60	155
Switzerland		1	102	78	181
Totals		2	459	340	801

Similarly, we show the counts for the different age groups per country in Tables 3 and 4 for panel and EBU participants respectively.

Table 3. Age distribution for panel sample.

	Age	18-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60-69	70-100	Totals
Country								
Austria		42	42	39	43	33		199
Belgium		34	56	43	45	46	1	225
France		174	155	161	165	155		810
Germany		205	199	186	242	199	1	1,032
Hungary		40	38	46	34	41		199
Italy		139	130	173	180	133	7	762
Portugal		41	37	44	43	36		201
Spain		108	114	136	127	95		580
UK		184	180	167	173	145	1	850
Totals		967	951	995	1,052	883	10	4,858

Table 4. Age distribution for EBU-recruited individuals.

	Age	18-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60-69	70-100	Totals
Country								
Czech		10	18	24	13	5	4	74
Germany		8	5	10	21	11	4	59
Hungary		11	27	50	22	19	7	136
Italy		8	12	18	21	16	3	78
Lithuania		11	21	20	11	13	1	77
Macedonia		2	1	12	18	7	1	41
Portugal		17	32	44	31	18	13	155
Swiss		8	17	25	52	51	28	181
Totals		75	133	203	189	140	61	801

Finally, the distributions for education are also presented here:

Table 5. Education distribution for panel sample.

Education	none	elementary school	middle school or apprenticeship	high school	university	Totals
Austria	1	37	66	35	60	199
Belgium	9	21	78	23	94	225
France	57	57	253	160	283	810
Germany	15	239	431	114	233	1,032
Hungary		15	117	15	52	199

Italy		13	210	393	146	762
Portugal	10	41	64	24	62	201
Spain	4	50	79	188	259	580
UK	59	45	307	173	266	850
Totals	155	518	1,605	1,125	1,455	4,858

Table 6. Education distribution for EBU-recruited individuals.

Education	none	elementary school	middle school or apprenticeship	high school	university	Totals
Czech		7	9	29	29	74
Germany	1	3	16	10	29	59
Hungary		12	52	8	64	136
Italy		4	6	39	29	78
Lithuania		2	22	22	31	77
Macedonia		9	20	8	4	41
Portugal	2	15	51	17	70	155
Swiss	4	11	67	37	62	181
Totals	7	63	243	170	318	801

3 Usage – Case example

The Connected and Autonomous Vehicle Acceptance Assessment Tool is designed as a modular tool for usage for a variety of research, industry development, and policy related questions regarding the acceptance of CAVs. For this, the items can be chosen individually to create surveys of varying lengths to be able to be employed with minimum administrative effort and in a very economical manner. A few examples follow.

3.1 Example 1: Privacy concerns

Example 1: Researching privacy concerns of citizens in Germany and Spain and how they relate to general attitudes towards CAVs.

If a researcher wanted to investigate German and Spanish citizens' privacy concerns with CAV introduction, they could employ the following two items, with a polarity scale from 1 to 7.

1. If I used autonomous vehicles, my personal data would be...
less secure x1 x2 x3 x4 x5 x6 x7 more secure.
2. If I used autonomous vehicles, the risk that my personal data were misused would be
higher x1 x2 x3 x4 x5 x6 x7 lower.

The researcher might then collect data from samples of German and Spanish citizens, and compare the averages over these two items; they could afterwards also compare their findings with the benchmark values provided in Chapter 5.

In addition, the researcher might want to know whether these privacy concerns are related to citizens' general evaluation of CAVs. They could add some items on general evaluations to their survey:

3. The thought of autonomous vehicles is generally...
[disconcerting x1 x2 x3 x4 x5 x6 x7 promising]
4. My spontaneous attitude towards autonomous vehicles is...
[very negative x1 x2 x3 x4 x5 x6 x7 very positive]

The researcher could then check if there is a correlation between participants' privacy concerns and their general evaluations of CAVs.

3.2 Example 2: Safety and intention to use CAVs

Example 2: Researching safety expectations of citizens of different ages and whether this might relate to citizens' intention to use CAVs in the future

If researcher wanted to investigate citizens' safety expectations related to the vehicle usage after CAV introduction, they could employ the following two items, with a polarity scale from 1 to 7.

1. If large sections of the population used autonomous vehicles, travel for all citizens would be...
More dangerous x1 x2 x3 x4 x5 x6 x7 less dangerous.
2. If large sections of the population used autonomous vehicles, the number of traffic accidents would be
higher x1 x2 x3 x4 x5 x6 x7 lower.

If the researcher wanted, in addition (or instead) to know about safety expectations related to road co-users, they could employ the following two items:

3. If large sections of the population used autonomous vehicles, pedestrians would be...
more at risk x1 x2 x3 x4 x5 x6 x7 less at risk.
4. If large sections of the population used autonomous vehicles, the number of traffic accidents involving pedestrians, bicyclists or other road co-users would be
higher x1 x2 x3 x4 x5 x6 x7 lower.

The researcher might then consider collecting data from citizens of their country across a wide variety of ages and compare the averages of these items between for example younger citizens and senior citizens; they could then compare their findings with the benchmark values provided in Chapter 5.

In addition, the researcher might want to know whether safety expectations might be related to intention to use CAVs. They could add the following items, with a Likert scale from 1 to 7 (completely disagree to agree completely):

5. If autonomous vehicles were available, I would use them.
6. I would try to avoid autonomous vehicles as much as possible.
7. I would not like to use autonomous vehicles.
8. I would be willing to use autonomous vehicles.

The researcher could then check if there is a correlation between participants' safety expectations and their intention to use CAVs.

4 Indices and metrics for assessment items

4.1 Confirmatory factor analysis – introduction and prerequisites

The following chapter will describe the confirmatory factor analysis executed on the data collected from the survey described in chapter 2, as well as, first, the prerequisites necessary to carry out this analysis.

A confirmatory factor analysis is a multivariate statistical procedure. CFA for short, it is used to test how well a number of theoretically pre-defined constructs are represented by the measured variables. Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) is different from an Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) in that the latter explores and provides information about the numbers of factors required to represent the data. To carry out the CFA, we a priori specified the number of factors in order to confirm previously exploratorily proposed model of CAV acceptance (Kacperski et al, 2021) and then iteratively checked for improved loadings to arrive at the best model.

As mentioned, before conducting the CFA, we report the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure, which is a measure of Sampling Adequacy, and the correlation matrix of items, below.

The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure (KMO) indicates the proportion of variance in variables that might be caused by underlying factors. The higher the values (which can be close to 1.0), the more it is indicated that a factor analysis may be useful. Table 7 showcases KMOs for each item in the survey. It can be observed that all items are close to 1.0, which is a very good outcome - this indicates that a factor analysis is recommended in order to find latent higher-level factors.

Table 7. Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measures for items.

Item	KMO
ACCESSIBILITY_assistance	0.97
ACCESSIBILITY_disabilities	0.98
AFFECT_travelexp	0.98
COUSER_SAFETY_acc	0.95

COUSER_SAFETY_ped	0.96
DATA_PRIVACY_misuse	0.87
DATA_PRIVACY_secure	0.87
EMISSIONS_ghg	0.87
EMISSIONS_pollution	0.87
JOB_PERFORMANCE	0.98
LIFE_SAT	0.98
ROAD_SAFETY_all	0.97
ROAD_SAFETY_nr	0.95
SOCIAL_LIFE_events	0.96
SOCIAL_LIFE_friends	0.95
TRAVELOSTpj	0.89
TRAVELOST_mob	0.89
TRAVEL_TIME_	0.97
TRAVEL_TIME_faster	0.96
Ease_handle	0.93
Ease_problems	0.9

The next table displays the correlation matrix, which is a table that displays all correlations (from -1 to 1) of the individual items with each other. A higher correlation indicates that variables have a linear relationship with each other, i.e., a positive correlation means two variables increase together, whereas a negative correlation indicates that when one variable increases, the other decreases. It can be observed in the table that all variables correlate positively with each other, and that some correlations are quite high, for example road co-user safety regarding accidents; road co-user safety regarding pedestrian safety, and road safety in general.

Item correlation matrix

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21
1 COUSER_SAFETY_acc	1	0.44	0.47	0.77	0.8	0.47	0.49	0.45	0.4	0.48	0.41	0.39	0.58	0.48	0.43	0.82	0.47	0.46	0.37	0.49	0.4
2 TRAVEL_COSTpj	0.44	1	0.35	0.44	0.42	0.37	0.34	0.48	0.34	0.29	0.28	0.34	0.33	0.33	0.74	0.43	0.3	0.51	0.19	0.28	0.21
3 TRAVEL_TIME_	0.47	0.35	1	0.5	0.46	0.48	0.44	0.32	0.4	0.37	0.37	0.36	0.51	0.47	0.35	0.47	0.59	0.33	0.26	0.38	0.3
4 ROAD_SAFETY_all	0.77	0.44	0.5	1	0.77	0.53	0.55	0.45	0.43	0.51	0.45	0.4	0.65	0.54	0.44	0.8	0.52	0.46	0.37	0.54	0.43
5 COUSER_SAFETY_ped	0.8	0.42	0.46	0.77	1	0.47	0.49	0.43	0.41	0.47	0.4	0.39	0.58	0.47	0.42	0.78	0.47	0.43	0.34	0.49	0.38
6 JOB_PERFORMANCE	0.47	0.37	0.48	0.53	0.47	1	0.59	0.32	0.44	0.44	0.47	0.4	0.6	0.61	0.38	0.49	0.56	0.33	0.33	0.47	0.32
7 SOCIAL_LIFE_events	0.49	0.34	0.44	0.55	0.49	0.59	1	0.3	0.43	0.47	0.46	0.41	0.61	0.7	0.33	0.5	0.57	0.31	0.33	0.49	0.33
8 EMISSIONS_pollution	0.45	0.48	0.32	0.45	0.43	0.32	0.3	1	0.25	0.31	0.24	0.26	0.32	0.31	0.47	0.48	0.27	0.77	0.2	0.26	0.23
9 DATA_PRIVACY_secur	0.4	0.34	0.4	0.43	0.41	0.44	0.43	0.25	1	0.26	0.38	0.77	0.49	0.45	0.37	0.39	0.46	0.26	0.16	0.39	0.26
10 ACCESSIBILITY	0.48	0.29	0.37	0.51	0.47	0.44	0.47	0.31	0.26	1	0.35	0.24	0.48	0.47	0.27	0.49	0.41	0.31	0.33	0.37	0.28
11 LIFE_SAT	0.41	0.28	0.37	0.45	0.4	0.47	0.46	0.24	0.38	0.35	1	0.35	0.54	0.5	0.27	0.42	0.47	0.26	0.25	0.43	0.32
12 DATA_PRIVACY_mis	0.39	0.34	0.36	0.4	0.39	0.4	0.41	0.26	0.77	0.24	0.35	1	0.46	0.42	0.36	0.37	0.43	0.26	0.17	0.35	0.25
13 AFFECT_travelexp	0.58	0.33	0.51	0.65	0.58	0.6	0.61	0.32	0.49	0.48	0.54	0.46	1	0.64	0.34	0.59	0.62	0.32	0.37	0.58	0.44
14 SOCIAL_LIFE_friends	0.48	0.33	0.47	0.54	0.47	0.61	0.7	0.31	0.45	0.47	0.5	0.42	0.64	1	0.33	0.49	0.6	0.31	0.33	0.49	0.33
15 TRAVEL_COST_mob	0.43	0.74	0.35	0.44	0.42	0.38	0.33	0.47	0.37	0.27	0.27	0.36	0.34	0.33	1	0.43	0.3	0.49	0.19	0.28	0.21
16 ROAD_SAFETY_nr	0.82	0.43	0.47	0.8	0.78	0.49	0.5	0.48	0.39	0.49	0.42	0.37	0.59	0.49	0.43	1	0.47	0.48	0.38	0.5	0.4
17 TRAVEL_TIME_faster	0.47	0.3	0.59	0.52	0.47	0.56	0.57	0.27	0.46	0.41	0.47	0.43	0.62	0.6	0.3	0.47	1	0.28	0.33	0.46	0.33
18 EMISSIONS_ghg	0.46	0.51	0.33	0.46	0.43	0.33	0.31	0.77	0.26	0.31	0.26	0.26	0.32	0.31	0.49	0.48	0.28	1	0.2	0.26	0.21
19 ACCESSIBILITY_assist	0.37	0.19	0.26	0.37	0.34	0.33	0.33	0.2	0.16	0.33	0.25	0.17	0.37	0.33	0.19	0.38	0.33	0.2	1	0.31	0.33
20 Ease_handle	0.49	0.28	0.38	0.54	0.49	0.47	0.49	0.26	0.39	0.37	0.43	0.35	0.58	0.49	0.28	0.5	0.46	0.26	0.31	1	0.63
21 Ease_problems	0.4	0.21	0.3	0.43	0.38	0.32	0.33	0.23	0.26	0.28	0.32	0.25	0.44	0.33	0.21	0.4	0.33	0.21	0.33	0.63	1

4.2 Confirmatory factor analysis - results

Below is the result of the confirmatory factor analysis, calculated for the two available samples, sighted and visually impaired participants. Note that these are different from the participant samples described in 2.3, as those had split along recruitment by panel and EBU; some panel participants were visually impaired, and some EBU recruited participants reported not having a visual impairment. Splitting the samples along the actual presence of visual impairment seemed more sensible in this case.

4.2.1 Factor loadings

First, the model factor loadings are displayed in Table 8. The first column displays the sample visual impairment (sighted vs visually impaired); the second and third column show the factors that were extracted (Safety, Cost, Efficiency, Sustainability, Independence, Privacy, Ease of Use) and which items loaded onto these factors. The fourth column displays the loadings (bolded).

Loadings above 0.5 are considered acceptable, and loadings above 0.7 are considered very good. As can be seen in the table, we achieve very high loadings in the majority of items onto their factors.

Standard errors, z-values, p-values and low/high confidence intervals are reported in columns five to nine. However, the loadings are the most important statistic to consider here.

Table 8. Model factor loadings.

VI	Factor	Item	Loading	SE	z	p	L CI	H CI
S	safety	ROAD_SAFETY_all	0.93	0.01	149.95	0	0.92	0.94
S	safety	ROAD_SAFETY_nr	0.92	0.01	143.84	0	0.91	0.93
S	safety	COUSER_SAFETY_ped	0.91	0.01	135.31	0	0.89	0.92
S	safety	COUSER_SAFETY_acc	0.91	0.01	142.27	0	0.9	0.92
S	cost	TRAVEL_COSTpj	0.91	0.01	60.62	0	0.88	0.93
S	cost	TRAVEL_COST_mob	0.88	0.02	57	0	0.85	0.91
S	efficiency	TRAVEL_TIME_	0.73	0.02	45.22	0	0.7	0.76
S	efficiency	TRAVEL_TIME_faster	0.87	0.01	69.09	0	0.84	0.89

S	sustainability	EMISSIONS_pollution	0.92	0.01	86.01	0	0.9	0.94
S	sustainability	EMISSIONS_ghg	0.92	0.01	84.32	0	0.9	0.94
S	independence	JOB_PERFORMANCE	0.8	0.01	58.5	0	0.77	0.83
S	independence	SOCIAL_LIFE_events	0.85	0.01	76.3	0	0.83	0.87
S	independence	SOCIAL_LIFE_friends	0.86	0.01	78.89	0	0.83	0.88
S	independence	ACCESSIBILITY_disabilities	0.82	0.01	56.25	0	0.79	0.84
S	privacy	DATA_PRIVACY_secure	0.93	0.01	69.64	0	0.91	0.96
S	privacy	DATA_PRIVACY_misuse	0.88	0.01	61.48	0	0.85	0.9
S	ease_of	Ease_handle	0.97	0.02	45.45	0	0.93	1.01
S	ease_of	Ease_problems	0.65	0.02	29.61	0	0.61	0.69
VI	safety	ROAD_SAFETY_all	0.92	0	319.4	0	0.91	0.92
VI	safety	ROAD_SAFETY_nr	0.92	0	345.9	0	0.91	0.92
VI	safety	COUSER_SAFETY_ped	0.9	0	276.33	0	0.89	0.9
VI	safety	COUSER_SAFETY_acc	0.92	0	329.17	0	0.91	0.92
VI	cost	TRAVEL_COSTpj	0.88	0.01	162.43	0	0.87	0.89
VI	cost	TRAVEL_COST_mob	0.88	0.01	164.5	0	0.87	0.89
VI	efficiency	TRAVEL_TIME_	0.78	0.01	108.07	0	0.76	0.79
VI	efficiency	TRAVEL_TIME_faster	0.82	0.01	122.04	0	0.8	0.83
VI	sustainability	EMISSIONS_pollution	0.89	0.01	163.21	0	0.88	0.9
VI	sustainability	EMISSIONS_ghg	0.91	0.01	164.07	0	0.9	0.92
VI	independence	JOB_PERFORMANCE	0.8	0.01	122.45	0	0.79	0.81
VI	independence	SOCIAL_LIFE_events	0.8	0.01	133.16	0	0.79	0.81
VI	independence	SOCIAL_LIFE_friends	0.81	0.01	135.36	0	0.8	0.83
VI	independence	ACCESSIBILITY_disabilities	0.66	0.01	69.27	0	0.64	0.68
VI	privacy	DATA_PRIVACY_secure	0.92	0.01	161.19	0	0.91	0.94
VI	privacy	DATA_PRIVACY_misuse	0.87	0.01	144.44	0	0.86	0.89
VI	ease_of	Ease_handle	0.95	0.01	107.21	0	0.93	0.97
VI	ease_of	Ease_problems	0.76	0.01	83.81	0	0.74	0.78

4.2.2 Fit indices

The following table displays fit indices and their cut-off values as required in the statistical literature (Hooper et al., 2007; Kline, 2005). As can be observed, the fit indices are far below or above their cut-off values, indicating that the model has excellent fit and has been chosen to correctly represent the data.

Table 9. Fit indices and cut-off values.

Fit index	Value	Cut-off values
chisq	1430.986	-
df	228	-
pvalue	0	-

gfi	0.998	> 0.9
cfi	0.998	> 0.9
rmsea	0.043	< 0.8
srmr	0.028	< 0.8
tli	0.998	> 0.9

In addition to the fit indices, the R-square values, i.e. the coefficients of determination, are reported in Table 10. The R-values are generally very high here as well, which is a very good sign that a good amount of variability is explained by our items; all items have a greater R-square than the cutoff value of 0.10 (Falk & Miller, 1992), with the lowest at 0.42.

Table 10 – R-square values as representation of variability explained.

Item	Sample	R-square
ROAD_SAFETY_all	Sighted	0.86
ROAD_SAFETY_nr	Sighted	0.85
COUSER_SAFETY_ped	Sighted	0.82
COUSER_SAFETY_acc	Sighted	0.83
TRAVEL_COSTpj	Sighted	0.82
TRAVEL_COST_mob	Sighted	0.78
TRAVEL_TIME_	Sighted	0.53
TRAVEL_TIME_faster	Sighted	0.75
EMISSIONS_pollution	Sighted	0.84
EMISSIONS_ghg	Sighted	0.85
JOB_PERFORMANCE	Sighted	0.64
SOCIAL_LIFE_events	Sighted	0.73
SOCIAL_LIFE_friends	Sighted	0.73
ACCESSIBILITY_disabilities	Sighted	0.67
DATA_PRIVACY_secure	Sighted	0.87
DATA_PRIVACY_misuse	Sighted	0.77
Ease_handle	Sighted	0.94
Ease_problems	Sighted	0.42
ROAD_SAFETY_all	Visually impaired	0.84
ROAD_SAFETY_nr	Visually impaired	0.84
COUSER_SAFETY_ped	Visually impaired	0.81
COUSER_SAFETY_acc	Visually impaired	0.84
TRAVEL_COSTpj	Visually impaired	0.77
TRAVEL_COST_mob	Visually impaired	0.78

TRAVEL_TIME_	Visually impaired	0.6
TRAVEL_TIME_faster	Visually impaired	0.67
EMISSIONS_pollution	Visually impaired	0.79
EMISSIONS_ghg	Visually impaired	0.82
JOB_PERFORMANCE	Visually impaired	0.64
SOCIAL_LIFE_events	Visually impaired	0.64
SOCIAL_LIFE_friends	Visually impaired	0.66
ACCESSIBILITY_disabilities	Visually impaired	0.44
DATA_PRIVACY_secure	Visually impaired	0.85
DATA_PRIVACY_misuse	Visually impaired	0.76
Ease_handle	Visually impaired	0.91
Ease_problems	Visually impaired	0.57

Finally, we assessed the discriminant validity of the latent variables by means of the heterotrait-monotrait ratio of correlations (HTMT), which can be found in Table 11. Discriminant validity means that two latent variables that represent different theoretical concepts are statistically different. Generally, a result less than 0.9 suggests that discriminant validity likely exists between the two scales (Henseler et al., 2015). However, as some of the factors do have relatively high ratios (up to 0.86 between independence and efficiency) it is not impossible to imagine that an overarching common factor of CAV acceptance might exist.

Table 11. Heterotrait-monotrait ratio of correlations for discriminant validity

	safety	cost	efficiency	sustainability	independence	privacy	ease of use
safety	1.00	0.6	0.70	0.58	0.75	0.51	0.64
cost	0.57	1.00	0.49	0.65	0.52	0.47	0.36
efficiency	0.70	0.49	1.00	0.45	0.86	0.61	0.60
sustainability	0.58	0.65	0.45	1.00	0.48	0.33	0.34
independence	0.75	0.52	0.86	0.48	1.00	0.59	0.66
privacy	0.51	0.47	0.61	0.33	0.59	1.00	0.45
ease of use	0.64	0.36	0.60	0.34	0.66	0.45	1.00

5 Benchmark values

5.1 Introduction to CAV Widget

To present benchmark values, an interactive widget was developed that allows interested parties to explore a large variety of benchmark values across the CAVA survey conducted. The widget can be found here and will be accessible until the end of the PAScAL project (Nov 2022):

https://pascal-survey.shinyapps.io/CAV_Acceptance/

The widget accesses the collected survey data and provides the ability to drag and drop the variables of interest in order to receive target value averages, sums and other aggregators of potential interest.

Displays can also be varied between simple tables as well as for example graphs and line charts.

5.2 Examples of Benchmark values – Age and Country

Table 12 presents average values for intention to use CAVs for panel participants, per country and age group, for usage of owned vehicles only. It can be observed that country differences are prominent (for example Portuguese participants are much more willing to use CAVs than for example German ones) and that even between younger and older participants, differences exist quite starkly (on average, younger participants seem more willing to use CAVs).

Table 12. Average intention to use autonomous self-owned vehicles across all ages.

Age	18-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60-69	Average
Austria	3.89	4.02	3.79	4.10	3.59	3.90
Belgium	4.45	4.11	3.20	3.48	2.97	3.61
France	4.53	4.03	4.00	3.69	3.62	3.98
Germany	4.23	4.19	3.89	3.49	3.48	3.86
Hungary	4.13	3.77	4.93	4.80	4.39	4.44
Italy	4.65	4.68	4.80	4.34	4.44	4.58
Portugal	5.01	5.08	4.67	4.38	4.85	4.81
Spain	4.46	4.45	4.64	3.77	4.26	4.34

UK	4.90	4.55	3.70	3.58	3.02	4.02
Average	4.51	4.35	4.17	3.80	3.77	4.12

Similarly, the average values can be displayed when the target vehicle is a shared vehicle: again, the same patterns appear, though the acceptance is in general a little lower than above.

Table 13. Average intention to use autonomous shared vehicles across all ages.

Age	18-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60-69	AVERAGE
AUSTRIA	4.07	4.39	3.84	3.42	3.30	3.86
BELGIUM	3.66	4.25	3.39	3.04	3.14	3.53
FRANCE	4.00	3.89	3.46	3.26	3.36	3.60
GERMANY	4.31	3.81	3.69	3.35	2.80	3.55
HUNGARY	4.04	4.71	3.72	4.35	4.61	4.28
ITALY	4.71	4.34	3.88	3.91	3.55	4.06
PORTUGAL	4.47	3.92	4.06	3.55	3.74	3.96
SPAIN	3.85	3.86	3.95	3.48	2.82	3.63
UK	4.25	4.06	3.37	3.16	2.49	3.50
TOTALS	4.20	4.05	3.69	3.46	3.09	3.70

As another example, we provide the expected consequences of CAV introduction for safety by participants across all countries from the panel sample when they expect that CAVs will be employed as self-owned vehicles. It can be observed that there are many differences across countries (for example, Hungary and Italy have much more positive expectations for safety than for example citizens from the UK or Austria), and that there are differences between potential users that are currently motorized or pedestrian; pedestrians seem to on average be a little more cautious about safety of CAVs than motorized participants.

Table 14. Average expected safety of autonomous owned vehicles across all countries.

	Car ownership	motorized	pedestrian	AVERAGE
Country				
Austria		4.32	3.93	4.27

Belgium	4.51	3.70	4.41
France	4.38	4.45	4.39
Germany	4.39	4.28	4.36
Hungary	5.06	5.12	5.08
Italy	4.99	5.53	5.02
Portugal	4.59	5.34	4.66
Spain	4.49	3.68	4.43
UK	4.11	4.12	4.11
AVERAGE	4.49	4.35	4.47

Deliverable 3.2 further discusses differences across a variety of research questions, for example socio-demographics, geographical differences, mobility behaviours and for participants with and without visual impairments.

6 Discussion and Limitations

The Connected and Autonomous Vehicle Acceptance Assessment Tool is a well validated and examined tool to assess CAV acceptance, in particular across a variety of important facets such as safety, sustainability, independence, ease of use, and for a variety of attitude measures, such as cognitive and affective evaluations, and intention to use.

In terms of limitations, it needs to be pointed out that the tool in its entirety might take between 7 and 15 minutes to complete depending on the reading speed of the participant (though participants with visual impairments might calculate with 2-3x this duration). Especially as an instrument to investigate citizen attitudes for policy making purposes, this might be too extensive. On the other hand, a major advantage of the tool can be seen in its ability to be used in an adaptive and modular manner. As described in Chapter 3, individual factors can be chosen if they are the target of investigations, and items can be selected to particularly evaluate those factors, including a possible comparison with benchmark values.

Further validation will need to be carried out, in particular with regards to construct validity and criterion validity, which would require further data collection cycles with inclusion of other well-validated instruments that have been developed to study similar concepts. Once CAVs are commonly experienced on the road, concepts like the actual usage behavior can be better studied. First forays into studying the validity of the tool within PAScAL have been undertaken when including some items in a study employing the IAT as well as in some of the simulations in WP4. Finally, one of the major limitations is its possible susceptibility to the passing of time – as further progress is made in the proliferation of CAVs on the roads, and as technologies develop, the CAVA might need updating or inclusion of further factors to represent additional areas of concerns and consequences. Researchers using the instrument should ensure to consider such shortcomings.

As an additional help, an interactive tool (i.e. a widget app) was developed to give potential future users of the tool access to a wide dataset of benchmark values to compare their own data collection against. This might also aid in these considerations.

In conclusion, the CAVA, as developed in WP3 over the course of the PASCAL project, has as its main aim to measure CAV acceptance via evaluation of expected CAV consequences and to provide further items to assess attitudes and intentions to use CAVs. The hope is that researchers, industry partners and policy makers will find it of use for their purposes.

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